

Research Article

Self-Bubbling Hydrogel for Uti: A Novel Solution with Amoxicillin and Corn Silk

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ABSTRACT

Urinary tract infection are among most common bacterial infection affecting individual worldwide The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of a novel floating hydrogel system embedded with self-generating micro-Bubbles for the efficient delivery of Amoxicillin Trihydrate Combined with natural therapeutic benefits of corn silk extract. The hydrogel system aim to enhance gastric retention time and improve localized delivery and bioavailability of drug at infection site. The incorporation. of microbubbles facilitates buoyancy and sustained release, while corn Silk Provide additional anti-inflammatory and diuretic effects. Comprehensive evaluation was carried out through physicochemical characterization, Swelling index, viscosity, drug release, MIC Test. The Presence of micro bubbles improved the internal Porosity and release kinetic, while corn sick extract contributed to an additional layer of therapeutic benefit. In conclusion, the formulated floating hydrogel system represents a promising approach for improving management of uti by combining the advantages gastroretentive delivery, natural adjunct of therapy, and controlled antibiotic release. This system could potentially reduce dosing frequency, enhance patient compliance. Urinary tract infections (UTIs) are a prevalent health concern globally, often requiring prolonged antibiotic therapy that may lead to systemic side effects and reduced patient compliance. This study aims to develop and evaluate a novel floating hydrogel system incorporating Amoxicillin trihydrate and corn silk (*Zea mays*) extract for targeted, sustained, and synergistic treatment of UTIs.

INTRODUCTION

Urinary Tract Infection: UTI is defined as microbial pathogens in urinary tract. A urinary

tract infection is one of the most common bacterial infections in woman. It is mainly caused by anatomy, sexual activity, short urethra, behavioral factor.

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The infection of bladder and urethra are referred to as infection of lower urinary tract, whereas kidney and ureter infection is as indication of upper urinary tract infection.

- Numerous pathogens, including both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and fungi, can cause urinary tract infections (UTIs). Women, children, and elderly patients who are otherwise healthy are usually the ones that suffer from simple UTIs.
- Indwelling catheters, anomalies of the urinary system, immunosuppression, or antibiotic exposure are typically linked to complicated UTIs. Uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* (UPEC) is the most frequent cause of both simple and complex UTIs. *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.
- *Staphylococcus saprophyticus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, group B streptococcus (GBS), *Proteus mirabilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*,

Staphylococcus aureus, and *Candida* spp. Are additional causal agents for uncomplicated UTIs, in order of prevalence.

- The other causal agents for complicated UTIs are *Enterococcus* species, *K. pneumoniae*, *Candida* species, *S. aureus*, *P. mirabilis*, *P. aeruginosa*, and GBS, in order of prevalence.

Types of Urinary Tract Infection:

- **Urethritis:** It is an infection to urethra and usually represents with painful urination.
- **Cystitis:** It is an infection to bladder and usually represents with abdominal pain, fever and blood in urine.
- **Pyelonephritis:** It is a serious type of infection which involves infection to kidney and it usually represents with backache, nausea, vomiting, pus forming in kidney.

UTI is mostly caused by bacteria *E. coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus faecalis*.

■ Signs of urinary tract infection:

- Pain in flank, abdomen, pelvic area
- Pressure in lower part of your pelvis

- Foul smelling pee
- Pain when you pee
- Frequent urination
- Blood in pee

REAL IMAGES OF URINARY TRACT INFECTION

TYPES OF DOSAGE FORMS IN MARKET TO TREAT UTI

Why Hydrogels?

You can see there are various dosage form available in market to treat UTI but we choose to form a floating hydrogel due to various Properties like:

Prolonged Residence Time: Floating hydrogel can remain in urinary tract for longer Period of time, allowing for sustained release of antibiotic.

↓

Target Delivery: It can be designed to target specific area tract of Urinary tract reducing its side effects.

↓

Effective against biofilms: Floating hydrogel can effectively target & eradicate biofilms which are common cause of UTI

Enhance Bioavailability: Floating hydrogel can enhance the bioavailability of antibiotic, allowing the lower doses.

Floating Hydrogel

- Hydrogel had been used as drug reservoir to extend the drug residence time in bladder. Due to the high viscosity of hydrogel serious problems are
- Urinary obstruction due to gel adherence
- Bladder irritation symptoms, such as blood clots in bladder.

This hydrogel, made of PEG and ammonium bicarbonate, stays liquid when cool but turns into a gel at body temperature. It forms bubbles that help it float in urine, preventing blockage and allowing slow, controlled drug release

- Intravesical instillation of drug solutions results into the elimination of drug solution from bladder after the first voiding of urine.

- To solve this problem floating hydrogel with self-generating micro-bubbles as a new delivery system very helpful for UTI.
- It floated in urine, avoiding the urinary obstruction and bladder irritation that ordinary hydrogels caused.

Characteristics:

- 1) Buoyancy: Floats on gastric (stomach) fluid
- 2) Controlled Drug Release: Releases medicine slowly over time
- 3) Stability in Acidic Conditions: Remains stable in stomach acid (low pH)
- 4) Lightweight Structure: Made with air pockets or low-density materials
- 5) Long Gastric Retention Time: Improves effectiveness of drugs meant for stomach absorption
- 6) Bioadhesiveness: Some types can gently stick to the stomach wall

Aim And Objective

Aim: To formulate floating hydrogel with self generating micro bubbles for treatment of UTI.

- Combination of synthetic and herbal drug (Amoxicillin trihydrate and corn silk) will give the better effect.
- Initially, Formulation will be in liquid form, when injected in body(ie.37) it gets converted into gel form
- Due to presence of ammonium bicarbonate (NH_4HCO_3) it forms microbubbles and flots on urine which leads to adhesion to the mucosa of urinary bladder.

- As the E-coli bacteria colonize on the mucosa of urinary bladder, the drug acts on it and inhibits the cell wall synthesis in the bacteria.

Rationale And Need

- Floating hydrogel is a novel drug delivery system which is site specific drug delivery system.
- It will work as a localized drug delivery system over systemic drug delivery.
- This formulation will give sustained release of drug in urinary bladder, which helps to reduce the frequent dosing.
- To overcome the disadvantage of other formulations for UTI, the floating hydrogel was prepared.
- Formulation will be introduced to patients by means of catheter. It is a suitable dosage form for bedridden patients, in case of complicated UTI.

Drug	Amoxicillin Trihydrate
Iupac Name	(2S,5R,6R)-6-[[[(2R)-2-amino-2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)acetyl]amino]-3,3-dimethyl-7-oxo-4-thia-1-azabicyclo[3.2.0]heptane-2-carboxylic acid; trihydrate
Molecular Formula	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅ S
Molecular Weight	365.4 g/mol
Solubility	In water
Appearance	Crystals of water
Melting Point	194°C
Pka	Strongly acidic – 3.23 Strongly basic-7.43

Justification of Drug and Excipient Drug:

- Amoxicillin is an antibiotic used for the treatment of bacterial infection.

- Highly soluble in water (hydrophilic) hence it is the best choice for the preparation of hydrogel.
- MOA: It inhibits cell wall synthesis, hence it helps to reduce the E. coli concentration.

Herbal Drug:

- Corn silk extract obtained from the corn that is collected from Zea mays

- It is used in the treatment of UTI

- It shows anti-inflammatory effect

- **Polyethylene Glycol (PEG 400)** – Humectant, Temperature sensitive gelation.

- **Carbopol 934** - Gelling agent, Thickening agent.

- **Ammonium Bicarbonate** - Bubble forming agent.

Preformulation Studies

Evaluation Tests

- Characterization of corn silk solution
- Melting and Determination of solubility
- UV Spectroscopy of drug
- MIC (Minimum Inhibitory Concentration)
- pH and Viscosity

- Effects of different pH

Characterization of Corn silk Solution:

By the visual appearance these observations were noted

□ Determination of Solubility:

Solubility of corn silk powder was tested in distilled water, ethanol, methanol, acetone.

- 1 gm of powder weighed accurately and dissolved in 10 ml solution. The solubility of Corn silk powder found in water.
- The corn silk powder solubility was checked in other solvent & the solubility observed were as

Sr. No.	Test	Result
1	Appearance	Smooth
2	Colour	Brownish
3	Odour	Sweet

Sr. No.	Solution	Result
1	Distilled water	Soluble
2	Ethanol	Insoluble
3	Methanol	Insoluble
4	Acetone	Insoluble

Melting point and Solubility of Drug

➤ Melting Point

Melting point of amoxicillin trihydrate was determined by the open capillary method.

The melting point noted was 192°C-194°C.

➤ Solubility:

Solubility of the drug was determined with the help of various solvents i.e distilled water, ethanol, methanol, acetone.

1 mg of drug weighed accurately and dissolved in 10 ml of various solvents

Solubility of drug found in water. In other solvents like ethanol, methanol, acetone it gave poor solubility.

Sr. No.	Solution	Result
1	Distilled water	Soluble
2	Ethanol	Very slightly soluble
3	Methanol	Slightly soluble
4	Acetone	Insoluble

UV

UV Spectroscopy

Amoxicillin trihydrate was analyzed by using UV at 226 nm.

Here 6.8 phosphate buffer was used for analysis of drug. R^2 was found to be 0.9932.

MIC

Here 5.6 gm of nutrient agar was added in 200ml of water and nutrient agar solution was prepared. The solution was sterilized in the autoclave for 45 min.

The nutrient agar solution was poured in the Petri plate, the plate was inoculated with E.coli. Plates were cooled, and then with help of borer well was formed in the plate.

Here 0.2 ml of drug solution of different concentration were poured in well i.e 40mg, 80mg, 120mg, 160mg, 200mg respectively.

The plates were incubated in the incubator for 24 hr Zone of inhibition was observed and recorded.

Evaluation

Sr. No.	Concentrations	Zone of inhibition
1	40 mg	8 mm
2	80 mg	10mm
3	120 mg	12mm
4	160 mg	15 mm

pH and Viscosity

pH

The pH of formulation was determined with the help of pH meter & it was found in the range of 6.75-6.80.

F1 batch showed 6.8 pH which was similar with the urine.

Sr.no	pH	Viscosity (Centipoise)
F1	6.8 ± 0.5	3370
F2	6.78 ± 0.5	3189
F3	6.79 ± 1.3	3200
F4	6.78 ± 1.1	3175
F5	6.74 ± 08	3120
F6	6.78 ± 1.2	3220
F7	6.71 ± 1.4	3201
F8	6.75 ± 0.9	3125
F9	6.74 ± 1.4	3130

Viscosity

The formulation should have an optimum viscosity that allows the ease of administration as liquid and produce satisfactory gel strength.

Viscosity was determined with the help of Brookfield viscometer. here spindle no 64_ was used to check the viscosity.

The viscosity of formulation are given in between 3120-3370 centipoise.

F1 batch shown the an optimum viscosity than other batches i.e 3370 centipoise.

BUBBLE SIZE

Bubble size was determined with the help of optical microscope.

Bubble size determination is important factor for the formulation because as the bubble size decrease it increase the foam ability of the formulation and also it is responsible to increase the resident time.

Bubble size was determined with the help of optical microscope. Bubble size of the particle should be in the range of 20µm – 400µm

(1)

(2)

Sr.No.	Length	Size
1	L1	277.117 micron
2	L2	313.257 micron

Effect of different pH on floating hydrogel

The 5ml of floating hydrogel was added in 200 ml of different pH solutions i.e 6,8,9

Here it showed that in any pH condition floating hydrogel float on solution. As shown in fig.

Plant Profile

- Plant : Corn Silk
- Kingdom: Plantae
- Family : Poaceae
- Genus : Zea
- Species : Mays

- Binomial name: Zea maize
- Uses: bladder infection, UTI, CHF, high blood Pressure
- Phytochemical constituents: proteins, potassium, resins, maizenic acid, fixed oil (oleum maydis)

HERE THE 4g OF CORNSILK POWDER WAS WEIGHED AND DISSOLVED IN 20 ml OF WATER

THE SOLUTION WAS BOILED FOR 15 MINS

NOW THE SOLUTION WAS COOLED AND FILTERED

FORMULATION METHOD (CORN SILK POWDER SOLUTION)

TEST FOR SAPONIN: POSITIVE

TEST FOR TANNINS: POSITIVE

TEST FOR PROTEIN: POSITIVE

TEST FOR ALKALOIDS: POSITIVE

TEST FOR FLAVANOIDS: POSITIVE

Sr. No	Phytochemicals	Test
1	Test for proteins (Millons test)	To the solution 5 ml of million's reagent was added . It gives white ppt, which turns brick red after warming it or ppt dissolves in solution and gives red color.
2	Test for Alkaloids (Dragendroff's reagent)	To the solution, dilute HCL was added. After shaking the solution was filtered. Treated with (Dragendroff's reagent) greenish yellow color precipitate indicated the presence of alkaloid.
3	Test for flavonoids	To the test solution, few drops of 95% ethanol, few drops of concentrated HCL and magnesium turnings were added. The appearance of orange colour shows presence of flavonoid .
4	Test for Tannins (Lead acetate test)	Solution was treated with few drops of lead acetate solution Yelow ppt indicated the presence of flavonoid.
5	Test for Saponins	Shake the solution vigorously with water, Persistant stable foam observed.

Formulation Method (Floating Hydrogel)

Here 4ml of PEG was added in distilled water and then 0.5g of ammonium bicarbonate & 0.5g of Carbopol 934 was weighed accurately

Add Amoxicillin was weighed accurately i.e. 200 mg & mixed in the above solution & stirred it, till it homogenizes.

In the above solution 1 ml corn silk solution was added & mixed it properly & stored it.

Simulated Urine

This ready-to-use solution has the same composition as Artificial Human Urine and closely resembles human urine.

Ingredients	Quantity
0.2M HCL SOLUTION	2 DROPS
AMMONIUM SOLUTION	0.1 ml

Simulated Urine

- Simulated urine (also called synthetic urine or artificial urine) is a laboratory-made liquid designed to closely mimic the chemical composition, appearance, and sometimes even the smell of real human urine.

- It typically contains: Water, Urea, Creatinine Salts (like sodium, potassium, and chloride) Sometimes uric acid or other compounds found in natural urine.

NACL	0.45 g
KCL	0.125 g
UREA	0.1g
CACL2	0.007 g
MAGNESIUM SULPHATE	0.005g

What Is Catheter?

- A Catheter is a thin, flexible tube that is inserted into body to remove urine blood or other fluids from body.
- It is also used to deliver medication and nutrients or other substances directly into the body.

Types Of Catheters:

Peripheral Venous Catheter

Central Venous Catheter

- 1) Direct access to the bladder
- 2) Localized treatment
- 3) Minimizing systemic absorption
- 4) Reducing risk of complication
- 5) Improve efficacy & Enhanced safety
- 6) Ease of insertion

Storage Conditions

Hydrogels should be kept in a temperature-controlled environment, ideally between 5°C to 27°C (41°F to 81°F) and in their original shipping plastic bag. For long-term storage, dry conditions may be preferred, while maintaining moisture can be achieved by storing in a sealed container in the refrigerator.

Storage Conditions

- **Dry storage:** Can preserve bioactivity for a longer period.
- **Moist storage:** Store in a sealed container in the refrigerator (4°C) to maintain hydration.

- **Light Exposure:** Protect from direct sunlight.
- **Avoid Freezing**
- **Temperature (Room Temperature):** Floating hydrogels are typically stored at 20°C to 25°C (68°F to 77°F) for most formulations.

Aseptic Techniques

□ Aseptic techniques are crucial in hydrogel formulation to ensure the sterility and safety of the final product, especially when the hydrogel is intended for biomedical or pharmaceutical applications. Here are some common aseptic techniques used in hydrogel formulation.

- Sterile Equipment
- Sterile Environment
- Sterile Ingredients
- Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)

Outcomes:

➤ Summary

Floating hydrogel is Novel drug delivery system. This drug delivery system maybe better than the other system, in case of bed ridden patient and unconcious patients.

- Also the use of synthetic and natural drug makes the better combination for UTI.
- This system will increase the resident time of drug in the urinary bladder.
- Advantage of the formulation is doesn't block the urethral opening due to its floating property , hence it doesn't stop urination.
- Increase in urination helps to remove toxicity from the body.
- As the resident time of drug increased the frequency of dosing also minimized.

CONCLUSION

□ It was concluded that floating hydrogel will be better drug delivery system for the unconscious patients.

□ It gives controlled drug release for longer period and help to minimize the frequent dosing to the patient.

□ This drug delivery system and formulation has the future scope for dealing with various diseases.

□ Floating hydrogel will be better option for UTI than Tablets, Capsules suspensions etc

□ The combination of synthetic and natural drug helps to reduce the side effect of synthetic drugs with desire effect.

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